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Twisting Effects on X-shaped Millimeter-wave Plastic Waveguides

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Abstract—This paper presents a theoretical and experimental study of the effects of a twist on the hybrid HE_{11}^V and HE_{11}^H mode propagations of X-shaped plastic waveguides. Plastic waveguides, providing a light-weight and low-cost alternative to optical fibers and copper lines for high data rate transmissions, are of high interest, particularly for applications in data centers and emerging autonomous cars. While the bending effects on plastic waveguides have been reported in the literature, to the best of the authors' knowledge, twisting effects were not addressed. The X-shaped plastic waveguide optimizing the sensitivity and loss trade-off compared to solid and hollowed circular plastic waveguides is considered in this study. First, the effects of a twist are analyzed in theory and simulation with an experimental validation. Then, the case of a twisted bent waveguide is investigated. The study concludes that for the X-shape topology, the polarization direction remains invariant (i.e., it does not rotate) in the two considered cases despite the twist.

Keywords—bending, electromagnetic analysis, millimeter wave propagation, plastic waveguides, polarization-mode, twisting.

I. INTRODUCTION

In recent years, plastic waveguides have raised a great interest from both the academia and the industry [1]-[4] due to the performance increase of millimeter-wave integrated circuits (MMICs) provided by advanced silicon technologies. Transmissions based on plastic waveguides achieving data rates in excess of 50 Gbits/s for ranges of few meters have been reported in the literature [5]-[9]. This emerging technology is particularly of high interest for applications in data centers and emerging autonomous cars.

Compared to metallic waveguides, one of the plastic waveguides advantages is their flexibility. The bending effects on such type of transmission lines have been reported in [10]-[14]. However, to the best of the authors' knowledge, the consequence of torsion was not addressed yet. Among other topologies, the X-shape plastic waveguide optimizing the sensitivity and loss trade-off compared to solid and hollowed circular plastic waveguides has been proposed in [2]. Contrary to other most common circular topologies, the behaviour of the hybrid modes of this particular topology is not trivial at first approaches. Furthermore, the effect of the material deformation due to twisting cannot be simulated and requires experimentation.

In section II, the twisting effects on the X-shaped waveguides are studied in theory, simulation and experiments. Then, section III introduces an experimental analysis of the effect of a twist on a bent plastic waveguide. Simulations presented in this paper were achieved using the CST microwave studio electromagnetic software.

Fig. 1. 3D views of the X-shaped plastic waveguides with their transitions to circular metallic waveguide (a) without and (b) with a θ twist.

II. TWISTING EFFECTS ALONG THE PLASTIC WAVEGUIDE

Fig. 1 illustrates a straight and twisted X-shaped plastic waveguide with its transitions to circular metallic waveguides.

The transitions are not only used in experiments to interconnect laboratory instruments, but also in simulations to guarantee the proper excitation with a waveguide port of the plastic waveguide modes, as part of the electromagnetic wave propagates in the air surrounding the plastic waveguide. The first end of the plastic waveguide is fixed (port 1). Whereas the second end (port 2) is rotated by a θ twisting angle (as shown in Fig. 1) resulting in a continuous twist along the plastic waveguide. The study is achieved in the WR-15 (50 to 75 GHz) frequency range. In this frequency range, the considered X-shaped plastic waveguide propagates the two orthogonal fundamental hybrid HE_{11}^V and HE_{11}^H modes illustrated in Fig. 2. In this study, the polarization of the modes is related to the port orientation as illustrated in Fig. 1. Therefore, the orientation of the HE_{11}^V and HE_{11}^H modes at the input port 1 are fixed. Whereas their orientation is rotated by the θ twist angle at the output port 2.

Fig. 2. Simulated E-fields of the (a) HE_{11}^V and (b) HE_{11}^H modes of the X-shape plastic waveguide, with $\rho_1 = 3$ mm, $\rho_2 = 2.7$ mm, $x = 0.6$ mm, and $y = 0.6$ mm.

Despite a twist, due to the topology of the X-shape waveguide, the equivalent relative permittivity ϵ_r seen at the center remains steady along the plastic waveguide. In addition, the topology is invariant, thus the cut-off frequency of the hybrid HE_{11} modes are constant and no upper mode propagates [15]. The transmissive amplitude carried by the HE_{11} modes is given by the follow matrix equation:

$$\begin{bmatrix} HE_{11,output}^V \\ HE_{11,output}^H \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} A_{11} & A_{21} \\ A_{12} & A_{22} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} HE_{11,input}^V \\ HE_{11,input}^H \end{bmatrix}, \quad (1)$$

$$\begin{cases} [A]_{ij} = R_\theta, & \text{if the polarization is going straight (case 1)} \\ [A]_{ij} = I_2, & \text{if the polarization follow the twist (case 2)} \end{cases}$$

With I_2 the unit matrix, R_θ the rotation matrix of θ angle. Considering the duality of the two orthogonal modes, the analysis is restricted to the study of the twisting effects on the HE_{11}^V mode. Thus, the variation for the HE_{11}^V mode transmission is given by the following equations:

$$\begin{cases} \Delta |S_{21,HE_{11,output}^V}|(\theta) = 10 \log_{10}(\cos(\theta) HE_{11,input}^V) & \text{(case 1)} \\ \Delta |S_{21,HE_{11,output}^V}|(\theta) = 10 \log_{10}(HE_{11,input}^V) & \text{(case 2)} \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

For validation from simulation and experimental results, a PTFE ($\epsilon_r = 2.1$, $\tan \delta = 2.10^{-4}$) X-shaped waveguide, operating at V-band (50-75 GHz) is considered. Its dimensions are given in Fig. 2. The transition from the plastic waveguide to the metallic circular waveguide used in simulations and measurements is detailed in Fig. 3.

Fig. 3. X-shaped plastic waveguide to circular metallic waveguide transition used in simulations and experiments: (a) front view and (b) cross-section view showing the 5 sections of the transition.

Its dimensions are given in Table 1. It is based on step-impedance matching sections.

Table 1. Length and diameter of the transition sections shown in Fig. 3.

Section i	1	2	3	4	5
L_i (mm)	2.4	1.3	6	2.8	4
D_i (mm)	8	7	6	5	4.2

To evaluate the effects of the twist, the transmission reference must be taken when the waveguide is not twisted. This allows to quantify the losses which are not related to the twist. Over the frequency range of interest (from f_{min} to f_{max}), the mean transmission variation for the hybrid HE_{11}^V mode due to the twist is calculated as follow :

$$\Delta |S_{21,HE_{11}^V}|(\theta) = \frac{1}{BW} \sum_{f=f_{min}}^{f=f_{max}} (S_{21}(f, \theta) - S_{21}(f, \theta = 0^\circ)), \quad (3)$$

with $BW = f_{max} - f_{min}$, the bandwidth, $f_{min} = 50$ GHz and $f_{max} = 64$ GHz in our experiment to guarantee a monomode bandwidth of the plastic waveguide which was optimized for the 60 GHz ISM band.

V-band measurements were achieved using a dc to 67 GHz two-port E8361A VNA from Agilent. A QOT- V16500 orthomode transducer (OMT) from QuinStar is used to isolate the HE_{11}^V mode from the HE_{11}^H mode at the output (port 2) and determine $\Delta |S_{21,HE_{11}^V}|$ using (3). Fig. 4 shows the calibration setup used for the experiment during calibration. It can be seen that a WR-15 horn antenna is connected to the second port of the OMT coupled to the HE_{11}^H mode. This antenna is used as a termination (since none were available in the facility). Prior, it was verified that the measurement was insensitive to the antenna environment. Thereby, the electromagnetic field carried by the HE_{11}^H mode at the output ($HE_{11,output}^H$) is radiated in the air. The control of the twist angle is made with a 5° step ruler engraved by the Wazer v1.5 water jet cutter used to fabricate the plexiglass holder. A Thru-Reflect-Line (TRL) calibration is used to de-embed the transitions and the OMT. The reference planes are shown in Fig. 4. Fig. 5 is a photograph of the experiment.

Fig. 4. Photographs of the measurement setup during calibration.

Fig. 5. Photographs of the measurement setup during experiments.

Fig. 6. Theoretical, simulated and measured $\Delta|S_{21}|_{HE_{11}^V}$ of the X-shaped plastic waveguide versus its twist angle.

The V-band measurement results are consistent with the theoretical case 1 and simulated results as shown in Fig. 6, independently of the plastic waveguide length and the frequency. A 3 dB variation is obtained for a 45° twist angle, i.e., at the output port, half of the amplitude of the HE_{11}^V is transferred to HE_{11}^H , the other half being coupled to HE_{11}^H . Therefore, despite a twist, the direction of the polarization does not rotate. A difference between the theoretical model and the measurement of 0.1 dB for a twist angle of 20°, 35° and 40° can be observed. This difference corresponds to an error of less than 1° which is due to the angle reading on the plexiglass holder ruler.

III. EFFECTS OF A SIMULTANEOUS TWIST AND BEND ALONG THE PLASTIC WAVEGUIDE

In this section, the effect of simultaneous twist and bend, as illustrated in Fig. 7, is analyzed. It has been demonstrated in literature that bending generates radiation for relatively small bend radius R . Also, bending is frequency-dependent, whereas this is not the case for twisting. This section demonstrates with simulation and measurement results that there is no correlation between the bending and twisting effects. V-band measurements, reported in Fig. 8, were carried out using the previous setup and a polystyrene plate allowing the control of the bend radius. Fig. 9 compares the $|S_{21}|$ for three bend radii R_i . Transmission losses in a back-to-back configuration are in the range of -3 dB for a 1-meter long plastic waveguide. As the frequency increases (i.e., wavelength decrease), the bending has smaller effects.

Fig. 7. 3D views of 90° bent X-shaped plastic waveguides with their transitions to circular metallic waveguide (a) without and (b) with a θ twist.

Fig. 8. Photographs of the measurement setup with a twisted bent X-shaped plastic waveguide.

Fig. 10 reports the mean variation of the $|S_{21}|$ parameter using (3). A good agreement between the theoretical, simulated and measurement results is obtained. Small deviations can be observed for bend radii of 5 cm and 11.5 cm. These deviations correspond to an angle deviation in between 1 and 3°. In

addition, because of the movement of the setup, fluctuations in the $|S_{11}|$, makes it challenging to achieve perfect calibration.

Fig. 9. Measured transmission of the 90° bent X-shaped plastic waveguide for three bend radii.

However, the twist effects trend and range of magnitude remains the same regardless of the bend radius. Therefore, the twist effects appear to be independent of the bend in the case of the X-shape plastic waveguide.

Fig. 10. Theoretical, simulated and measured $\Delta|S_{21}|_{HE_{11}^V, output}$ of the X-shaped plastic waveguide versus the twist angle and bend radius for a 90° bend.

IV. CONCLUSION

The effects of a twist on the hybrid HE_{11}^V and HE_{11}^H mode propagations of X-shape plastic waveguides were studied in this paper at V-band. The twisting effects have been analyzed in theory and simulation with an experimental validation. It is shown that the direction of polarization is invariant and does not rotate with the twist angle. Then, an experimental investigation demonstrates that the twisting effects are independent from the bending effects. Further investigations are currently underway with other types of plastic waveguide topologies.

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